

EVALUATING THE IMPACT OF SATELLITE DATA AVAILABILITY ON CROP CLASSIFICATION ACCURACY USING SENTINEL-1 AND RANDOM FOREST

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ABSTRACT

Ensuring sufficient food for the rising global population is a critical focus, especially given the current turbulent political circumstances. The first step for policymakers in addressing this issue is acquiring accurate crop maps. Modern Earth observation missions and advancements in data processing, particularly in machine learning, have enabled the successful generation of these maps. Although considered a traditional method nowadays, the Random Forest algorithm has consistently proven effective for crop classification tasks. Conversely, while synthetic aperture radar (SAR) satellite data lags behind optical satellite missions in terms of practical usage, its contribution remains significant. In this study, we combined Sentinel-1 data with Random Forest to classify nine crop types in Vojvodina, Serbia. Specifically, we assessed how varying amounts of information from radar satellites impact crop classification accuracy by analyzing three data availability scenarios: 1) single monthly acquisitions, 2) bi-monthly acquisitions (every 15 days), and 3) all available acquisitions. For the first two scenarios, bicubic interpolation was used. Out of 2399 parcels, 80% were used for training and validation (5-fold cross-validation), with the remaining 20% for testing. We calculated the mean value for each parcel and considered data acquisitions between April 1st and September 30th, 2021. The scenarios achieved overall accuracies of 90%, 94%, and 96%, respectively, with high precision and recall across nearly all classes, despite class imbalance. These findings underscore the potential of SAR data for classifying diverse crop types and highlight the possibility of reducing inputs for regional or global mapping typically characterized with high computational demands, while still achieving remarkable results.

Key words: crop maps, classification, Sentinel-1, random forest,